

Types of Small Architectural Forms

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Abstract:

The article is devoted to the history of the thousand-year development of small architectural forms. Exact dates were determined by oral examples from reliable documents and sources. Goals and functions are analyzed.

Keywords: small architectural forms, landscaping and urban planning.

1.Introduction. Small architectural forms (SAF, Street furniture) — auxiliary architectural structures, equipment and artistic and decorative elements, which have their own simple functions

and complement the overall composition of the architectural ensemble of buildings. Some of the elements of SAF do not bear utilitarian functions and have exclusively artistic and decorative purpose. Small architectural forms can play an important role in the architectural ensemble. In landscape design, they are one of the main elements of decorative garden design. Also, small architectural forms may include small structures made of lightweight structures

and installed temporarily, without a foundation (trade pavilions, etc.)

2. Methodology. Special attention should be paid to small architectural forms and recreational equipment. Small architectural forms (SAF) are small—scale structures and devices for seasonal and year-round use (stationary or transformable) designed to serve humans in an urbanized and natural environment. Small architectural forms have, as a rule, a utilitarian and artistic and decorative purpose, and some are only decorative. Among the buildings of a utilitarian nature are: shopping and information kiosks, all kinds of vending machines (telephone, newspaper), gazebos, pavilions at transport stops, shading structures (trellises,

pergolas, canopies), benches, etc. Among the structures of architectural and artistic purpose should be named supports for climbing plants, flower beds, trellises, trellises, spotlights, fountains, spray walls, etc. For example, the shape, size and color of the benches, as well as how they will be placed in combination with vegetation, terrain, pedestrian alleys and playgrounds, largely depend on the conditions of recreation for people and the aesthetic appearance of the area. The main requirement for the creation of small architectural forms is their integrated design and application using modular elements.

The main task of designing the SAF is to achieve stylistic generality with the help of uniform formative elements, a minimum number of types of building materials used.

3. Results and Discussion. The analysis of various types of small architectural forms and recreational equipment allows us to propose their general classification according to the following criteria:

- by age group (for children and adults);
- intended for normal people, for people with physical disabilities and the mentally retarded;
- for functional purposes — for all types of recreational activities (gaming, productive, sports, artistic and educational, educational, labor, motor);
- by the nature of the structural systems: frame, frame-panel, frame-tent, panel, frame-block, block-assembled, one-piece, pneumatic.
- When designing small architectural forms and equipment, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of structural systems:
- frame (the main structural elements are bars, rods, pipes; connections can be stationary or collapsible; material — wood, metal, plastic);
- frame-panel (instead of some parts of the frame, a panel element is used; the types of connections and material are the same as in the frame system);
- frame-awning (tarpaulin or leather, belts, plastic harnesses, strips are stretched on a rigid metal frame);
- panel (products are assembled from stationary or collapsible shields, shields can be made of wood or plastic);
- frame-block (blocks that act as additional elements are attached to the base frame);
- block-assembled (the product is assembled from two or more molded elements made of polymer materials or reinforced concrete);
- Solid block (products are made of a whole stamped or cast block; material — polymers, reinforced concrete).

Small architectural forms should be placed in accordance with the degree of their compositional activity, taking into account the laws of composition.

Qualitative characteristics of the IAF:

- compliance with the functional purpose;
- constructive expediency
- modularity of elements, creation of a mobile transforming environment
- color unity and the unity of the materials used;
- Artistic expressiveness and imaginative impact.

Leisure furniture is widely used in the formation of landscape objects: various types of benches, pergolas, shade canopies, gazebos, urns. Each small form should be used only in accordance with the function for which it is intended to be used. They have mainly a functional purpose, but also have a significant impact on the spatial organization of any territory.

Conclusion. When designing small forms of architecture and other elements of landscaping, it is advisable to focus on sets of modular block elements of simple configuration and small sizes (40...50 cm in height), which will allow for the early production of individual products that can be assembled locally from 3-4 block elements of 10-12 different small forms of architecture. This is especially necessary for the improvement of newly introduced residential areas on the principle of an urban development complex. When placing SAF on the territories of small gardens, it should be remembered that in creating a harmonious human habitat, nevertheless, the main role should belong to arrays of greenery, individual decorative groups of trees, water surfaces, and relief geoplastics. When creating any landscape compositions, it is undesirable to collect in one territory several different small shapes with an acute, but sharply different shape from each other (for example, several benches of different shapes and designs, etc.).

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